

Time Series Analysis Application on Industry 4.0: PreCoM Project

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Abstract

Purpose - Industry 4.0 is triggering the implementation of new technologies on industrial settings, enabling the use of data-based techniques and thus opening new opportunities to apply statistical models to predictive maintenance. In this paper we present a new Time Series Analysis software module for the evaluation of the condition of machine components.

Design - The TSA module can use different models to operate under both continuous and low volume productions. In both cases the strategy consists on fitting a predictive time series model to a variable that indicates the condition of a target component. Then, forecasts can be computed and compared with a severity limit in order to estimate its condition.

Findings - The application to the monitoring of industrial environments of a fixed time series forecasting methodology can have a positive impact on maintenance decisions. However, a certain level of customization to each machine and component is needed in order to get the best results.

Practical implications - Updated and more precise information about the condition of machines can improve their availability and reduce maintenance costs.

Originality/value - The main value of the work is the development and application of a predictive maintenance software that is flexible for multiple conditions and can be executed without user intervention.

Keywords: Time Series Analysis, ARIMAX, Predictive Maintenance, Condition Based Monitoring, Industry 4.0.

1 Introduction

PreCoM is a three year Industry 4.0 (see (Pereira & Romero 2017) and (Saucedo et al. 2018)) project, funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme, which aims to deploy and test a predictive cognitive maintenance decision-support system to improve preventive maintenance and ultimately increase in-service efficiency of machines. Currently, more powerful and cheaper sensors, together with Big Data Analytics, offer a unique chance for monitoring the condition and performance of machines and tools. In order to make intelligent decisions over elements of an industrial environment, it is highly important to have a complete knowledge about it and its ambient conditions. Other fields unconnected to production, specially those closely connected with technology sectors, are much more advanced in terms of digitization and data analysis. This allows for better decision making and increased efficiency. In an industrial environment the information needs to be retrieved from the machines, and this can be done through sensors. Thus, the evolution of sensors and instrumentation not only enable industrial progress, but also is its driving force, see (Schütze et al. 2018). The PreCoM project takes advantage of new technologies on smart sensing, by constructing a Internet of Things network that offers brand new options for monitoring the condition and performance of machines and tools. This is the foundation for developing a predictive maintenance system.

Preventive maintenance aims to intervene before a failure or a decrease in performance occurs, by scheduling periodic maintenances. However, this approach can be too conservative, as most of the time technicians find no problems during periodic maintenances, see (Hashemian 2011). Unnecessary stoppages are an issue in itself, as they introduce an unnecessary cost. Also, they are not the only shortcoming of a preventive maintenance approach, as between maintenances, industrial systems are not being evaluated. In contrast, with predictive maintenance (Selcuk 2016), the condition of machine components is estimated through data generated by sensors, so intervention is produced at the right time. This information-based approach brings a better decision making, avoiding unnecessary equipment replacement and improving availability and efficiency, ultimately reducing production costs. Most of the time the degradation pattern is not suitable for preventive maintenance, being predictive maintenance the better approach to deal with failures and degradation of components, see (Hashemian 2011). For these reasons, research and innovation under predictive maintenance in the Industry 4.0 is following an upper trend. A review of the state-of-the-art can be found in Zonta et al. (2020).

PreCoM offers a predictive maintenance solution from the beginning to the end of the process, i.e., from the data gathering through sensors to the display of results to the end user. The system developed at PreCoM can identify and localize damages, determine its severity, predict its evolution, estimate life times, reduce the probability of false alarms, enhance damage detection, issue warnings to carry predictive maintenance tasks and improve the efficiency of machines activity. The specific objectives are (www.precom-project.eu):

- Increment availability and maintainability.
- Increment the time invested on predictive maintenance.
- Reduce accidents due to failures.
- Reduce the unnecessary energy consumption.
- Reduce the raw material excess waste.

PreCoM has more than 20 different modules, and their integration would constitute the system described above. In this paper we present the Time Series Analysis (TSA) module, which computes near-future predictions for the value of chosen variables related to the condition specific critical components. Then, these forecasts are used to assess the component’s future condition by estimating the probability of exceeding a given/certain severity threshold. The latter is a value that introduces a criteria to define the normal and fault states of the target component. The goal is to evaluate the status of the industrial equipment and predict failures or wear, so, along with the information provided by other modules, offer improved maintenance recommendations.

Over the last decades, the application of TSA models (estimation and forecast) to predictive maintenance has been validated on many industrial environments. Some of the examples found on the scientific literature are (Amin et al. 2013), (Chen et al. 2019), (Ho & Xie 1998), (Ordóñez et al. 2019) and (Pham & Yang 2010). A similar strategy to the one we propose here, where a failure threshold indicates the condition of the target component, can be found in (Lu et al. 2001), (Lu et al. 2007) or (Wu et al. 2007). In order to apply a TSA model to industry we need to select those models that are consistent with the available information, estimate the unknown parameters using historical data and evaluate the forecast accuracy.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we discuss the statistical methodology proposed for two different contexts: low volume production and continuous production. In Section 3 we review the integration of the developed software on the PreCoM system. In Section 4 we present two examples of application, one with real data and other with simulated data. Conclusions are discussed in Section 5.

2 Statistical methodology

The ability to predict a failure on a critical component has a great impact on industrial settings, as this allows to apply predictive maintenance instead of preventive or reactive maintenance. Such predictions can be calculated by using data collected through condition based monitoring. We focus on cases where sensors provide measurements (vibrations, temperatures, power consumption,...) that can assess the condition of a component, which would be applicable in many scenarios. We will refer to the variable for which measurements are taken as condition monitoring variable.

The observations of the condition monitoring variable are taken sequentially in time. Thus, we have a time series and TSA can be performed, see (Box et al. 2015). TSA can identify patterns in data and use them to provide forecasts, which could be used to assess component condition. Our proposal consists on evaluating the expected value for the near future with TSA forecasts and return the probability of exceeding a given threshold. This limit, that represents the maximum safe value for the condition variable, should be provided as a technical specification of the component, and must be specified by the user in other cases. Then, the system will trigger warning messages depending on the obtained probability of exceeding the threshold and the established alarm levels.

As the condition variable is being continuously monitored, forecasts could be updated every few minutes. In practice, the frequency of execution would depend on the context and user preferences, but being able to update the condition of the component in real time would allow to react to both sudden and gradual issues before they arise.

Next, we describe the TSA techniques proposed for the two situations we had to deal with in the project.

2.1 Continuous production

Here we describe the most common situation, where the target machine is continuously working. In this case, many variables such as vibrations would naturally adapt to classic time series models. Instead of using the values of each measurement, we have chosen to aggregate the data. The main factor behind this decision was to enhance the stability of the data, reducing the variance and improving the estimations. Also, the aggregation period was chosen as the frequency of execution, so that the forecasts would match the following updates.

The statistical Time Series Analysis model we have selected is the ARIMAX family of models (Box et al. 2015). Let $\{Y_t\}$ be the time series where Y_t represents aggregated measurements at time t . First, an Autoregressive Moving Average model ARMA(p, q), where p represents the order of the autoregressive part and q the moving average one, can be represented as:

$$Y_t = \mu + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + e_t - \theta_1 e_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q e_{t-q}.$$

The parameters refer to the deterministic (μ), autoregressive (ϕ), moving average (θ) and error (e) components, where e_t is assumed to be white noise. We define white noise as an stationary process of zero mean and constant variance (σ_e^2). ARMA models are suitable only for stationary time series, see (Hamilton 1994), so in case of trend, a generalization of these models must be considered: Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). A series $\{Y_t\}$ follows an ARIMA(p, d, q) process if the d -th regular differentiation of Y_t follows an stationary and invertible ARMA(p, q) process. Let's define:

- $BY_t = Y_{t-1}$ (lag operator).
- $\Phi_p(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B^1 - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p$.

- $\Theta_q(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B^1 - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$.

The stationarity and invertibility conditions for the model are that the complex roots of $\Phi_p(B)$ and $\Theta_q(B)$ lie outside the unit circle. Then, an ARIMA(p, d, q) model can be represented in compact notation as:

$$\Phi_p(B)(1 - B)^d Y_t = \Theta_q(B)e_t.$$

ARIMA models are commonly used in the analysis of vibration signals, which many times will be the condition variable, see for example (Wu et al. 2007), (Yang et al. 2017). In many cases, more information could be added to the model in the way of exogenous variables. For example, type of production or machine temperature. The use of exogenous variables could improve the forecast accuracy. Thus, we propose an Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with Exogenous Variables (ARIMAX) model, which extends the ARIMA model by including one or more exogenous covariates. Let $\{X_t\}$ represent the covariate (we include only one covariate in the model). Then the ARIMAX(p, d, q) model is defined as:

$$\Phi_p(B)(1 - B)^d Y_t = \beta X_t + \Theta_q(B)e_t. \quad (1)$$

2.1.1 Forecasts: bootstrap

TSA models can produce forecasts from the autocorrelation structure they have identified. While there are theoretical results, see (Box et al. 2015), on how to obtain the expected mean value of the series, in order to compute prediction bands the distribution of the error must be known, and normality cannot always be assumed. Therefore we compute the forecasts through a Monte Carlo simulation by means of a smoothed bootstrap on the residuals, see (Shao & Tu 1996). Let $y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$ be the data from which future values are being forecasted and $e = (e_1, \dots, e_n)$ the residuals from the ARIMAX model. The former can be expressed from the latter through (1), being then e_t the source of variability in an ARIMAX model. The algorithm to obtain forecasts up to horizon h is described below:

1. (a) If there is one or more covariates on the model, (let (x_1^r, \dots, x_n^r) be the values of the r exogenous time-varying covariate and $\hat{\beta}_r$ the corresponding estimated parameter, for $r = 1, \dots, R$), then the series is transformed to the residuals of the regression:

$$\epsilon_t = y_t - \sum_{r=1}^R \hat{\beta}_r x_t^r$$

- (b) If $d > 0$, then the series is differentiated d times, where the differentiation is defined either as $(\nabla y_t = y_t - y_{t-1})$ or $(\nabla \epsilon_t = \epsilon_t - \epsilon_{t-1})$, depending if (a) applies or not. The result is the differentiated series $z = z_{d+1}, \dots, z_n$.
If $d = 0$, then $z = y$ (or $z = \epsilon$ in case (a) applies).

2. In order to apply smoothed bootstrap to the residuals, e , we first resample with replacement and then add a small perturbation from a normal kernel. From $t = (n + 1), \dots, (n + h)$, a random e'_t from $e = (e_1, \dots, e_n)$ and a random s_t from a Normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_e^2/10)$ are selected. Then the bootstrap sample is defined as:

$$e^* = (e_1^*, \dots, e_{n+h}^*) = (e_1, \dots, e_n, (e'_{n+1} + s_{n+1}), \dots, (e'_{n+h} + s_{n+h}))$$

3. From each bootstrap sample e^* , we can compute the series trajectory according to the model with estimated parameters $\hat{\phi}_1, \dots, \hat{\phi}_p, \hat{\theta}_1, \dots, \hat{\theta}_q$:

$$z_t^* = \sum_{i=t-p}^{t-1} \hat{\phi}_i z_i' + \sum_{j=t}^{t-q} \hat{\theta}_j e_j^*, \quad t = (n + 1), \dots, (n + h),$$

where

$$z_i' = \begin{cases} z_i & \text{if } i \leq n \\ z_i^* & \text{if } i > n \end{cases}$$

4. If steps 1(a) or 1(b) are applied, then the reverse transformations are performed on z^* , obtaining the trajectory y^* , which is on the correct scale.
5. Steps 2, 3 and 4 are repeated B times to generate as many different trajectories as desired. For large enough B , bootstrap provides a quite good approximation.
6. The following results are computed:
- *Expected value*: For each horizon, from 1 to h , the mean value on the trajectories at that horizon is calculated. This is the main result, as a forecast for the future values of the series.
 - *95% Prediction bands*: The upper and lower limits are obtained the same way as above, but calculating the quantiles instead of the mean.
 - *Probability of exceeding T* : Let T be a given threshold. Then, the estimated probability of exceeding T at horizon t is computed from the empirical distribution function assembled from all trajectory values at that horizon (\hat{F}_{tB}), see (Shao & Tu 1996). The result is a vector of probabilities

$$\hat{p}_t = \mathbb{P}(y_t > T) = 1 - \hat{F}_{tB}(T), \quad t = (n + 1), \dots, (n + h).$$

Figure 1 shows an example of the algorithm results. From the original time series (in grey), many trajectories were simulated (represented in different colors). Then, the expected value forecasts and 95% prediction bands (black) were obtained.

Figure 1. Example of bootstrap forecasting algorithm. In grey, original time series. In different colors, simulated trajectories. In black, expected value forecasts and 95% prediction bands.

2.1.2 Outlier detection

Real data are often noisy, since there are many factors on industrial settings that can affect the measurements but cannot be sensorized. In order to identify the correct patterns in data, it is important to reduce the noise by removing outliers. Here we focus on the effect of level shifts, as these are the most common type of outliers we have encountered. Anyway, other types of outliers in time series (additive outliers, innovative outliers and temporary changes) could also be detected if the case required it.

The traditional procedure to detect outliers on TSA models is the one described in (Chang et al. 1988), where the outlier effects are detected and evaluated one by one. Nevertheless, this method suffers from potential masking and spurious issues. So we followed the procedure in (Chen & Liu 1993), which performs a similar outlier effects estimation (one by one), within an inner loop. The final estimation, however, is obtained from an outer loop that jointly estimates all the effects and the model parameters.

2.2 Low volume production

The ARIMAX models are appropriate for discrete equally-spaced intervals of time, see (Box et al. 2015). Nevertheless sometimes the machine or the target component is not under continuous production and its use is irregular. This would be the case, for example, of a machine with several tools, but where only

one acts at a time. If we were interested on monitoring each tool, or some of them, separately, ARIMAX models would not be a good choice.

Our proposal for this situation is to, first, aggregate data by each independent usage of the machine-component and, second, perform a regression model where the last observation is added as one of the covariates. In this context, the linear regression assumption of normality of the error will not always be satisfied. Because of this, the proposed model is the Generalized Linear Model (GLM), see (McCullagh & Nelder 2015), which is a flexible generalization of linear models that allows for response variables with non normal error distribution. A link function establishes the relationship between the linear predictor and the distribution function. The logarithmic function is an example of link function, and one that we have found useful.

Consider $\{Y_t\}$ the time series composed by the aggregated measurements of a target condition monitoring variable, where each value corresponds with the mean value of sequentially ordered usages in time and let $\{X_{1_t}\}, \dots, \{X_{d_t}\}$ be covariates. Then, the simplest GLM model with link function $g(y)$ and including an autoregressive component is given by:

$$g(Y_t) = \mu + \beta_0 Y_{t-1} + \beta_1 X_{1_t} + \dots + \beta_d X_{d_t} + \epsilon_t.$$

This model, however, can be further improved. One way this could be done is by modelling the covariates as polynomials. Define the family of polynomials:

$$p_i(x) = \beta_{i1}x + \beta_{i2}x^2 + \dots + \beta_{im_i}x^{m_i}, \quad i = 0, \dots, d,$$

where m_i is the degree of the i -th polynomial. Then, we propose a generalized polynomial autoregressive model (GPAM) of the form:

$$g(Y_t) = \mu + p_0(Y_{t-1}) + p_1(X_{1_t}) + \dots + p_d(X_{d_t}) + \epsilon_t. \quad (2)$$

Polynomials can model nonlinear relationships between variables. This, together with the many choices available as link function can offer great versatility to model different problems. In practice, in PreCoM, we have found useful cubic polynomials (i.e. $m_i = 3 \forall i$) and $g(y) = \log(y)$ as link function.

Once the model is fitted, predictions can be computed by smoothed bootstrap in a similar way as the previous section. Let $x_1 = (x_{1_{n+1}}, \dots, x_{1_{n+h}}), \dots, x_d = (x_{d_{n+1}}, \dots, x_{d_{n+h}})$ be future values for covariates $\{X_{1_t}\}, \dots, \{X_{d_t}\}$ up to an horizon h . Also let $Z_t = g(Y_t)$ be the transformed response variable and $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_n)$ the residuals from the GPAM model (they are on the scale of Z_t). If y_n is the last observation for $\{Y_t\}$, then predictions can be computed as follows:

1. For $t = (n + 1), \dots, (n + h)$, a random ϵ'_t from ϵ and a random s_t from a Normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2/10)$ are selected. Then the bootstrap sample is defined as:

$$\epsilon^* = \left(\epsilon_{n+1}^*, \dots, \epsilon_{n+h}^* \right) = \left((\epsilon'_{n+1} + s_{n+1}), \dots, (\epsilon'_{n+h} + s_{n+h}) \right)$$

2. The value of $\{Y_t\}$ at time $t - 1$ is needed to compute the predictions at time t , as it is entered the GPAM model as a covariate.
 - (a) For the first value, y_{n+1} is known: y_n .
 - (b) For $t = (n+2), \dots, (n+h)$, y_{t-1} it is estimated by the previous value, $y_{t-1}^* = g^{-1}(z_{t-1}^*)$.
3. A trajectory at the transformed variable scale, $z^* = z_{n+1}^*, \dots, z_{n+h}^*$, can be computed from (2) by using the values obtained at steps 1 and 2. Note that ϵ_t is replaced by its bootstrap version, ϵ_t^* .
4. Steps 1, 2 and 3 are repeated B times, generating as many trajectories as needed to provide a good approximation of the distribution of the predictions. Each trajectory is reverse transformed to the original variable scale:

$$y^{*b} = g^{-1}(z^{*b}), \quad b = 1, \dots, B.$$
5. Predictions are computed from the bootstrap trajectories the same way as in Section 2.1.1, step 6.

3 Software: integration, automation

The statistical models described above were programmed in R (R Core Team 2019). This programming language is open-source and offers a large variety of statistical tools that have been of great usefulness. Also, it can be combined with other software and automated for production with no problems.

Our TSA software is a component of a bigger system in PreCoM, where it is referred to as TSA module. Because of this, the code is adapted to fit in with the rest of the project's software. As stated before, the goal of the module is to predict future values of a monitoring variable to evaluate the condition of the monitored component. This is done by checking the probability of the variable exceeding a threshold in the near future. Then, this information can be used by PreCoM, together with other modules, to assess the status of the machine and make maintenance recommendations. As a part of a bigger whole, the TSA module is not made to be handled by an user. Instead, it has been built to be called by other routines and work in an automatic way, providing results continuously. This last part is of great importance, as the focus of the TSA analysis is to detect short term changes in component condition. The part of the software that will be continuously computing results is the so called *online* part, whereas the part that will, from time to time, improve and update the statistical models is the so called *offline* part. The software receives as input for both parts data directly from the cloud, which is gathered in real time by sensors.

3.1 Overview of the software

The software comes in the form of two main files, one for the offline part (`TSA_offline.R`) and other for the online part (`TSA_online.R`). They both can be executed from command line, so in practice they are called by third functions.

3.1.1 Offline part

The objective of the offline part is to generate an appropriate time series model for the condition variable. Thus, the most updated model is stored as an RDATA file, so it can be used by the online counterpart.

Also a descriptive summary of all models is saved as a text file. It contains useful information such as the models coefficients or the detected outliers. Every time a model is fitted, the file is automatically updated. A plot of the data used to fit the model is saved too. Only the first file (model) will be used by the rest of the software, but the other two files could be interesting in case the technical staff need, at some point, to validate the models or to better understand a result.

3.1.2 Online part

The online part computes predictions for the condition variable using the models saved in the offline part.

The main output of the module is a table stored with CSV format, which contains the expected value forecasts, the 95% prediction bands and the probabilities of exceeding the threshold fixed in the offline part, together with the alarm levels obtained from this probabilities. A precise threshold selection is important in order to establish the alarm levels consistently and, therefore, improve maintenance recommendations. The alarm levels go from 0 to 4:

- **0:** No damage.
- **1:** No serious damage, await.
- **2:** Probable damage, await.
- **3:** Examine the device whenever you can.
- **4:** Maintenance should be planned.

Furthermore, a PDF report is generated. There, the same table available in the CSV file and a plot of the prediction with prediction bands are provided.

3.1.3 Required software

The main software the TSA module requires is **R** ($\geq 3.6.1$) (R Core Team 2019). The libraries that need to be installed on R are: *forecast* (≥ 8.9), *htmlwidgets* (≥ 1.3), *httr* ($\geq 1.4.1$), *jsonlite* (≥ 1.6), *plotly* ($\geq 4.9.0$), *R.utils* ($\geq 2.9.0$) and *tsoutliers* ($\geq 0.6 - 8$).

Further libraries and software are needed to assemble the PDF output report. The additional R libraries are: *kableExtra* ($\geq 1.1.0$), *knitr* (≥ 1.23), and *rmarkdown* (≥ 1.14). The secondary software required is: L^AT_EX, Pandoc, Perl and Ghostscript.

3.2 Integration with Cloud

All the machines monitored by PreCoM have installed an heterogeneous data gathering system composed by accelerometers and other devices that generate in real time a complete database for condition monitoring. PreCoM's cloud infrastructure manages all the data from different sources and enables its access from TSA and other modules of the project safely and efficiently.

The communication with the cloud is done by a REST API (Masse 2011). These are widely used to build HTTPS applications. Under our context, the most important operation of this system is GET, which allows to read data from the cloud by passing the correspondent URL and headers. Then, the data is obtained in JSON format, which consists on attribute-value-pairs and array data types. A data gathering R script is responsible for the connectivity with the API. It generates the request based on the time period and variables from which data is needed. Then, data is handled by a JSON parser, organized and delivered to the statistical tools.

3.3 Integration with PreCoM system

We described above how the software is connected with the cloud and how it obtains input data from condition variables. Next we will detail how it is integrated with the PreCoM system, and how it will be used in production.

First, the modules will be located and running in Docker containers, which are a standard unit of software isolated from the rest of the system that can run a process reliably and quickly. They contain all the software needed to run an application. The purpose of containers is being able to independently run different processes and offer an enhanced developing environment which can be deployed in different systems. They operate in a similar way as virtual machines, but whereas Docker containers share the host OS kernel, each Virtual Machine has its own OS, sharing only the hardware resources of the host. In practice, containers are more portable and efficient as they have no guest OS and less resource overhead (Bashari Rad et al. 2017).

The module is ran through Bash scripts containing a call to R and the arguments needed. It is important to launch the execution in an automatic way, so the execution of these files is scheduled. This is done by following a different scheduling for the two parts (online and offline), that can vary depending on the needs of each case.

There is no fixed recommendation on how often to execute the offline part as it strictly depends on the case. If the target signal has big variations from hour to hour, an update every few hours could be reasonable, as this way the fitted model captures the latest behaviour more precisely. However, if the signal

evolution is more stable, updates could be done much less frequently (daily or weekly, for example). In contrast, the online part should be executed more frequently (every few minutes, for example) to be continuously producing new predictions. The goal of the online part is to provide condition based monitoring in real time.

Observations are usually available per second, however, for a better performance, we propose to aggregate data by frequency of execution. If, for example, forecasts are to be updated each five minutes, then the recommendation would be to aggregate data in five minute blocks. The software itself is able to automatically perform this aggregation to the raw data collected from the cloud.

When an output is generated, the container (client) sends it to the PreCoM central server by the data transfer protocol FTP. This server is called PreCoM Brain, and manages the information of the different PreCoM modules. Here, information located at the TSA CSV output file, like probabilities of failure, could be accessed, as well as information from other sources, to evaluate component condition and make maintenance recommendations. Furthermore, the most updated PDF report is passed to the Product Line Information Visualization (PLIV) Application, which offers to the production line manager a concise and comprehensive visualisation of the state of the production enhanced by the evaluations performed by PreCoM.

Figure 2 shows a diagram that summarizes the application of TSA module in production for condition based monitoring. We recap the process, step by step:

1. Target machines have sensors installed on their critical components. Data is sent to the cloud and stored.
2. Every few days/hours (depending on the case), the offline part is executed for all condition variables. Historic data is collected from the cloud, by using the API, so TSA models can be updated. All models are stored locally, in the Docker containers, but they can be accessed if needed.
3. Every few minutes, the online part is executed for all condition variables. In this case only the most recent data is collected from the cloud, again, through the API. This data, together with the models saved at step 2 is used to forecast the expected values, prediction bands, probabilities of exceeding the threshold and alarm levels. These results are returned both in CSV and PDF formats (table and report).
4. The online outputs are sent from the Docker containers to the PreCoM Brain. They must be sent as soon as generated, since they provide information for the near future.

4 Applications

Here we present examples to illustrate the two statistical methodologies proposed. To ensure the confidentiality of the PreCoM industrial partners infor-

Figure 2. Diagram representing the integration of the TSA module.

mation, we will not use data from the machines where the TSA module is being applied. Instead, we use a real reference data set for continuous production and simulated data for low volume production. The simulations have been inspired by real cases in PreCoM.

4.1 Continuous production

We use the the Milling data set (Agogino & Goebel 2007) to illustrate the predictive algorithm described in Subsection 2.1. The source of the data set is the NASA Ames Prognostics Data Repository, a collection of data sets contributed by universities, companies or agencies covering data that can be used for development of prognostic algorithms. Mostly, the data sets consist on run-to-failure time series, which are suitable to a condition based monitoring and therefore TSA module can be tested as a component condition predictor.

The Milling data set represents sixteen experiments performed on a milling machine under various operating conditions. The target component is the milling tool, and its degradation was investigated by measuring the flank tool wear. Also, several variables as power consumption or vibration were monitored. The number of runs at each experiment was dependent on the degree of flank wear that was measured between runs at irregular intervals up to a wear limit (and sometimes beyond). Please, see (Goebel 1996) for further details on the experiments and data acquisition. The overcome of a 0.6mm flank wear for the milling tool was considered as the failure condition.

The variables we use in this analysis are:

- *VB*: Flank wear in mms, measured after runs; Measurements for VB were not taken after each run.

Figure 3. Scatterplot of RMS smcAC with respect to VB. Blue corresponds with cast-iron material and red with steel. The lines correspond with linear model trends.

- *Time*: Duration of experiment (restarts for each case).
- *DOC*: Depth of cut, with two levels. The highest is the double that the lowest (does not vary for each case).
- *Feed*: Feed, with two levels. The highest is the double that the lowest (does not vary for each case).
- *smcAC*: AC spindle motor sensor, in V.
- *material*: Material that can be cast-iron or steel (does not vary for each case).

The variable *smcAC* consists on a curve with 9000 points for each run. This information was summarized by means of the Root Mean Square (RMS) of those values. We define it as a condition variable for the flank wear *VB*, as the more wear, the more power the spindle motor will consume. This effect can be seen in Figure 3, a scatter plot by material type (cast-iron and steel), with linear trends. In both cases there is an upward trend coherent with the previous statement. The 0.6mm *VB* limit is generally exceeded for higher values of *RMS smcAC*. A threshold of $T = 2.3$ was selected, such that if the power consumption exceeds this value, it is considered an indicator of critical flank wear. From now on, a separate analysis will be performed for the two material categories: cast-iron and steel. Figure 4 represent the histograms of *RMS smcAC* data for both materials. We observe that, while mean and quartiles are similar, the distributions for each material are slightly different. Both are asymmetric, but cast iron data has less tailedness (excess kurtosis of -0.5 compared to 0.69). Also, for the cast-iron material, the 94-th observation is a severe outlier, so it was not represented on the graphs.

Figure 4. Histograms for RMS *smcAC*. Left, cast-iron material. Right, steel material.

The relationships with the other variables are visually explored in Figure 5. First, *DOC* can have two values, 0.75 and 1.5. For both materials, two boxplots of *RMS smcAC* are represented, corresponding with the two *DOC* levels. A clear difference on the variable distribution can be inferred from them. The

Figure 5. Correlation graphs for the covariates with respect to $RMS\ smcAC$. On the left, DOC , on the center, $Feed$, on the right, $Time$. Blue corresponds with cast-iron material and red with steel. 94-th observation of cast-iron material was not represented.

same occurs with the $Feed$ variable. On this case, the levels are 0.25 and 0.5, and, while the dissimilarity is lower than in the previous case, it seems to be significant based on the boxplots. Finally, the $Time$ variable is continuous, thus the correlation is explored through a scatter plot. While there is not a clear pattern, the power consumption generally increases with the duration of the experiment. All variables have an effect on the power consumption, so they will be incorporated as covariates in the time series model.

The former analysis is not part of PreCoM's TSA module, but a required step for each new application. Not only each machine and working conditions are unique, but the type of data can vary from case to case. Then, understanding these elements is necessary to customize the solution offered by the TSA module so it is used to its fullest potential.

The TSA module was applied to both cases (cast-iron and steel), saving 10 observations as test sample to validate the accuracy of the predictions. The best ARIMAX model was selected according to Akaike information criteria (AIC), which is a relative measurement of statistical model quality, see (Box et al. 2015). For both materials, an ARIMAX(1, 0, 0) was selected. Even if the time series has a clear trend, in these models it is explained through the correlations with other variables. A summary of both models is displayed in Figure 6. The covariates, $Time$, $Feed$, and DOC are significant for both materials. $Feed$, and DOC were included in the model through a dummy variable that is 1 when they take the higher of their levels and 0 when they take the other. In the cast-iron case, the outlier at position 94 was modelled also through a dummy variable following the treatment described in (Chen & Liu 1993).

```

CAST-IRON MATERIAL MODEL SUMMARY
Regression with ARIMA(1,0,0) errors

Coefficients:
      ar1  intercept      Time  Feed_0.5  DOC_1.5      A094
      0.8016      0.5340  0.0169   0.4218   0.8252  21.7790
s.e.  0.0611      0.0811  0.0008   0.0666   0.0714   0.1165

sigma^2 estimated as 0.01803:  log likelihood=60.3
AIC=-106.61  AICc=-105.36  BIC=-88.51

Training set error measures:
              ME      RMSE      MAE      MPE      MAPE
Training set 0.003470524 0.1300911 0.0962330 -0.2437095 6.305692
              MASE      ACF1
              0.156679  0.004957968

```

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STEEL MATERIAL MODEL SUMMARY
Regression with ARIMA(1,0,0) errors

Coefficients:
      ar1  intercept      Time  Feed_0.5  DOC_1.5
      0.6117      0.6407  0.0455   0.7501   0.7234
s.e.  0.1608      0.0905  0.0032   0.0824   0.1117

sigma^2 estimated as 0.02764:  log likelihood=20.42
AIC=-28.84  AICc=-26.79  BIC=-17.61

Training set error measures:
              ME      RMSE      MAE      MPE      MAPE
Training set 0.005866115 0.1573594 0.109207 0.2777545 6.595364
              MASE      ACF1
              0.4176412 -0.1122105

```

Figure 6. ARIMAX model summaries for cast-iron (top) and steel (bottom)

Figure 7. Top: Forecasts (blue) for cast-iron material. Bottom: Forecasts (blue) for steel material. The red line corresponds with threshold $T = 2.3$ on both graphs

For the cast-iron case, the train error is small, less than 10% compared to mean (1.87). The error in the steel case is slightly higher, but still relatively small and below 10% of the mean (1.7). In order to check if the models correctly modelled the time series, lag 1 autocorrelation Ljung-Box tests (Box et al. 2015) were performed. The p-values were 0.9603 (cast-iron) and 0.4226 (steel), so the autocorrelation modelling was effective.

Figure 7 represents, for the two materials, the complete *RMS smcAC* time series (train+test) together with forecasts for the test part, along with 95% prediction bands. They have been computed with the algorithm presented in Subsection 2.1.1. The threshold of $T = 2.3$ is represented in red as a severity limit in both graphs. Probabilities of exceeding it offer an assessment on the flank wear.

In the first case (cast-iron), predictions fit precisely the real *RMS smcAC*. As a predictor of the condition of the flank wear, the alarm level does not indicate

	Cast-iron				Steel			
	VB	Pred.	$\mathbb{P}(y_t > T)$	AL	VB	Pred.	$\mathbb{P}(y_t > T)$	AL
1	0.17	1.342	0.000	0	0.37	1.937	0.059	1
2	0.2	1.448	0.000	0	0.48	2.057	0.100	1
3	0.24	1.554	0.000	0	0.56	2.153	0.186	2
4	0.32	1.657	0.000	0	0.70	2.263	0.381	3
5	NA	1.708	0.001	0	NA*	2.477	0.838	4
6	0.4	1.777	0.004	0	NA	2.700	0.979	4
7	0.45	1.882	0.016	0	0.24	2.917	0.999	4
8	0.49	1.983	0.056	1	NA	3.143	1.000	4
9	0.58	2.085	0.150	2	0.40	3.368	1.000	4
10	0.65	2.204	0.340	3	0.62	3.593	1.000	4

*At horizon 5, on the steel case, a tool change was produced.

Table I. TSA results for both materials. The alarm levels (AL) description can be found in Section 3.1.2

the need of an immediate maintenance action. Probabilities of exceeding T are small for the near future, but they increase for longer-term horizons. This is consistent with the real flank wear values, as at horizon 10 they are starting to reach critical values (0.65mm).

The forecasts for the steel case, even though not as precise as the previous one, are still remarkably precise. In addition, the prediction bands and exceeding probabilities are a good estimator of tool condition. The alarm level reaches the value 3 (*Examine the device whenever you can*) at horizon 4, and from horizon 9 the alarm level is 4 (*Maintenance should be planned*). These results match well with the flank wear measurements, which take values up to 0.7mm.

A more detailed summary of the TSA module results is given in Table I. In practice, it is important to emphasise that the interpretation of the warning level highly depends on the horizon. Let's assume that time between horizons is 10 minutes, and that the sixth prediction has a critical warning level, but not the previous ones. This would mean that in an hour, the condition variable could likely be high enough to trigger a warning, but not in the immediate future. So the recommended course of action would be to remain vigilant about the evolution of the variable, that should have updated TSA results each 10 minutes under the conditions described above. As tool wear is a gradual process, if a maintenance action was needed, it could be indicated by the TSA module more definitely on its following updates.

4.2 Low volume production

For low volume production, we simulated data inspired by a real case, similar to the one we have analyzed during our work in the PreCoM project. Low volume

Figure 8. Simulated data: positions and mean vibrations

production refers to machines that operate irregularly, so our simulated data replicates a tool that performs runs with varying times between them. Each run corresponds with a circular trajectory where the tool operates on 120 different well defined points. Eleven runs were simulated (See Figure 11 in Appendix A). The condition variable would be the tool vibration, on mm/s, which would be influenced on the two dimensional position, that is incorporated to the model as covariate. Ljung-Box autocorrelation tests were performed to both raw data, and residuals from a regression of the vibration on the position, proving that the simulated data is highly autocorrelated. The reason behind using the residuals is to eliminate the effect that the position could have on the vibration values before realizing the tests.

In Figure 9, the points where the tool operates are represented, as well as the mean vibration of each one. The first point would be the correspondent with $\alpha = 0$ and then the tool would operate counter clockwise. On a situation like this, it could be very useful to simplify the X-Y position by the angle α , as no information is lost. So that would be the first step on this analysis.

However, taking into account that vibration seems to reach the highest values at three equidistant points on the circumference, even a better simplification could be performed. The behaviour could be interpreted as the high-level vibrations having a frequency of three times on the circumference. Taking this

Figure 9. Graphic representation of the sinusoid transformation $f(\alpha)$.

into account, the following sinusoid transformation is proposed to provide an improved representation of the position:

$$f(\alpha) = \cos\left(3\left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{3}\right)\right) \quad (3)$$

Note that, by subtracting $\pi/3$ in (3), $f(\alpha)$ is close to one in high vibration areas with angles $\pi/3$, π and $5\pi/3$, as represented in Figure 9. As the cosine function has domain $[-1, 1]$, the transformation is able to filter the location information, by representing what is related with vibration levels in a clearer way. This allows for a better modelling.

Ten of the simulated runs were selected as training data, and the remaining one will be used as test data. The GPAM model described in Subsection ?? was fitted, using $f(\alpha)$ as covariate, a logarithmic link function and cubic polynomials. In addition to this model, we have also fitted a GPAM model with logarithmic link function and α as covariate and a GPAM model with identity link function and α as covariate.

Then, forecasts were computed for the last 30 points of the test run from all models. In Table II, the MAE of these forecasts are represented. The model with the lowest MAE is the proposed one, where the link function is the logarithm and

Link \ Cov	Cov	
	α	$f(\alpha)$
Logarithm	0.265	0.306
Identity	0.307	-

Table II. MAE for the three GPAM models considered, depending on the chosen covariate and link function.

Figure 10. Forecasts (blue) for the test run. The red line corresponds with threshold $T = 4.5$

$f(\alpha)$ is the only covariate. Taking into account that the mean vibration of all runs was 2.52, the error is just slightly above 10% with respect to it. Therefore, even if the predictions could be further improved, they offer a solid estimator of future values, specially taking into account that they were computed for 30 steps ahead. The other two models have a very similar MAE, and, while the values indicate that the models could be useful, they are clearly not as precise as the first one. This result indicates that, on the one hand, having a logarithm as the link function allows for a better modelling and, on the other hand, using the transformed variable $f(\alpha)$ instead of the untransformed one positively impacts the model.

In Figure 10, the test run for the proposed model is represented, together with the expected value predictions and prediction band. Also, a representing a dummy threshold at 4.5. Forecasts effectively capture both position and autocorrelation effects. Table III displays the detailed results. They include a probability of surpassing $T = 4.5$ and a warning level, in a similar way as the previous section. This example, however, is not centred on the prediction of a failure, as it uses simulated data. Instead, it aims to validate the methodology proposed at 2.2 for prediction of future values, demonstrating it under the TSA module.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents a Time Series-based strategy to Predictive Maintenance, with two different approaches for two different scenarios: ARIMAX models for continuous production and GPAM models for low volume production. In both cases, the models, together with the threshold selection, offer solutions that

Forecasting horizon	Lower limit	Prediction	Upper limit	Probability of $y_t > T$	Warning level
1	1.462	2.089	3.456	0.003	0
2	1.580	2.341	3.851	0.008	0
3	1.696	2.539	4.134	0.015	0
4	1.833	2.704	4.461	0.024	0
5	1.926	2.847	4.679	0.031	0
6	2.034	2.980	4.825	0.038	0
7	2.111	3.095	5.066	0.048	0
8	2.225	3.204	5.149	0.059	1
9	2.273	3.301	5.318	0.075	1
10	2.318	3.350	5.469	0.078	1
11	2.336	3.375	5.456	0.085	1
12	2.336	3.369	5.374	0.082	1
13	2.304	3.317	5.343	0.075	1
14	2.233	3.238	5.271	0.068	1
15	2.157	3.130	5.161	0.053	1
16	2.055	3.023	5.057	0.049	0
17	1.976	2.892	4.838	0.039	0
18	1.871	2.771	4.621	0.029	0
19	1.782	2.644	4.423	0.023	0
20	1.690	2.532	4.224	0.018	0
21	1.614	2.435	4.158	0.017	0
22	1.547	2.348	3.959	0.012	0
23	1.494	2.279	3.868	0.011	0
24	1.452	2.237	3.832	0.009	0
25	1.435	2.197	3.755	0.008	0
26	1.419	2.177	3.757	0.008	0
27	1.409	2.156	3.663	0.007	0
28	1.397	2.150	3.631	0.008	0
29	1.399	2.142	3.656	0.006	0
30	1.397	2.147	3.678	0.007	0

Table III. TSA results for simulated data.

could be useful for a wide range of machines and components.

The most important part of the process is the definition of the problem, that has to be explained through condition variables. In all cases, an intensive analysis over the candidates for condition variable needs to be performed, so that the solutions proposed at this document can be adapted to best suit the particular problem. Once the definition of the problem is done, the TSA module can be applied with minimal user intervention, offering real-time automatic assessment for component condition.

The examples in Section 4 illustrate the methodology behind the TSA module and show its utility in an predictive maintenance environment. Also, it is being deployed within the PreCoM system on the use cases that are part of the project. More results over the TSA module will be available as the PreCoM project is demonstrated and further applied to industrial environments.

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A Low volume simulated data

Figure 11. Eleven runs of simulated vibration data, with respect to the position in radians.